

Re-Investigation of Cross Sections for (α, γ) Reactions on P -Nuclei ^{90}Zr , ^{121}Sb , ^{151}Eu , and ^{162}Er

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Abstract

Investigation of the cross sections for (α, γ) reactions on p -nuclei ^{90}Zr , ^{121}Sb , ^{151}Eu , and ^{162}Er was conducted by varying different α optical model potentials (α OMPs) while constraining the level density model (LDM) and radiative strength function (RSF) to the phenomenological constant temperature model (CTM) and the Kopecky-Uhl lorentzian (KUL) respectively. The calculations were performed within the framework of the Hauser-Feshbach theory, making use of the TALYS-1.96 code. Nuclear input model combinations were fine-tuned to regenerate the experimental data of cross sections. The present investigation was analyzed based on the root mean square error (*rms*). Good agreement was achieved for all nuclei under study. Based on the radiative capture cross sections, we have computed the thermonuclear reaction rates that can be used as inputs to various astrophysical models.

1 Introduction

Nuclei more massive than iron are formed in stars via the slow neutron capture process (s -process) and the rapid neutron capture process (r -process). These processes differ by their time-scales relative to the β decay and the density of neutrons [1]. The s -process is said to occur when the neutron capture time-scales are longer than β decay times. This constraint ensures that the product of slow neutron captures is a stable nucleus. The r -process, on the other hand, occurs when the neutron captures compete with β decays. The astrophysical environments for the s -process are asymptotic giant branch (AGB) and massive stars, each responsible for a contribution to the respective s -process components [2]. The sites for the r -process are not as established; they are hypothesized to occur in neutron star mergers and supernovae [3]. There also exist approximately 30 proton rich isotopes, known as p -nuclei. They are hypothesized to be produced by photodisintegration reactions on the products of neutron capture processes [4]. Since the lower binding energy of neutrons makes them easier to remove, photodisintegrations naturally lead to proton-rich isotopes. This p -process is thought to occur in supernova environments, though the sites have not yet been established [5].

Due to the limitations of theoretical models, the experimental measurements of these nuclei remain to be fully explained [6].

Gyurky *et al.* [7] measured the alpha capture cross sections for ^{151}Eu using the activation technique in the energy range (12 - 17) MeV. They further performed the statistical model calculations and found the predictions to be overestimated by a factor of 2. Kiss *et al.* [8] also employed the activation technique to measure the alpha capture cross sections of ^{162}Er in the energy range (11.21 - 16.09) MeV. Their investigated cross sections were in good agreement with the statistical model predictions. Kelmar *et al.* [9] measured the alpha capture cross sections for ^{90}Zr using HECTOR and the γ summing technique in the energy range (7.5 - 11.5) MeV. Their measurements were also complimented with the statistical model calculations, and the adjusted results were shown to agree well. Finally, Korkulu *et al.* [10] measured the alpha capture cross sections for ^{121}Sb using the activation technique in the energy range (9.74 - 15.48) MeV. Their measurements were then compared with the statistical model calculations and the theoretical predictions were found to be overestimated.

Recently, Nguyen Nhu Le [11] employed an α optical model potential (OMP) that uses double folding method to achieve high accuracy for α particle absorption width. The effects of the radiative strength functions (RSF) were studied on the p -nuclei ^{90}Zr , ^{121}Sb , ^{151}Eu , and ^{162}Er keeping the level density model (LDM) constant. The study concluded that the empirical SMLO model (SMLOg) and the global semi-microscopic (DIM+QRPAg) model regenerated the experimental data well, while the rest of the models produced higher deviations. In this study, we aim to investigate the predictions of the statistical model code TALYS-1.96 by fixing the LDMS and RSFs while varying the α OMPs. In the next sections, calculations and results are presented, leading to the conclusion.

2 Calculations and Results

Nuclear reactions involving targets beyond the iron peak are studied within the framework of the Hauser-Feshbach theory, also known as the statistical model [12]. The cross sections are directly related to the transmission coefficients in the incoming and outgoing channels. For the case of alpha capture reactions, the incoming channel is described by the α OMP. The optical model describes the interaction between the projectile and the nucleus. If our incident particle was, for example, a proton, the transmission coefficient would be provided by the proton optical model. In the case where the outgoing channels involve the emission of photons, their respective transmission coefficient is given by the RSF. The nuclear level density (LDM) needs to be folded in due to the large number of nuclear levels at excitation energies. This is because the information of individual levels is often either missing or incomplete for nuclei of astrophysical interests. In order to describe the (α, γ) reactions, we need the α OMP, a LDM and a RSF. If, for example, we were describing an (α, n) channel, there would be no need for the RSF. The reaction would be adequately described by an α OMP, a neutron OMP, and a LDM. The choice of the nuclear input models to the statistical model depend upon the channel we are trying to describe. Within the framework of the TALYS-1.96 code, the available α OMPs include the Normal potential, the potential of McFadden and Satchler, the potentials of Demetriou and Goriely, the potentials of Avrigeanu *et al.*, and the potential of Nolte *et al.* [13]. The phenomenological models have free parameters built-in that are vital in fitting

theoretical predictions with the experimental data. Since we aim to investigate the predictions of α OMPs, we fixed the LDM and RSF to the phenomenological constant temperature (CTM) and the Kopecky-Uhl (KUL) models respectively. The parameters were taken from the TALYS-1.96 structure database without any variations. The energies of both targets and projectiles obey the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution as the Quantum distributions reduce to it at the conditions of nucleosynthesis environments [14]. The astrophysical reaction rate is obtained by integrating the cross section over a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution of energies at the respective temperatures. The conditions of the astrophysical plasmas are such that the targets have a considerable excited state occupation probability. The relative populations of the various levels of nucleus obey a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. The reaction rate is expressed as

$$N_A \langle \sigma v \rangle^*(T) = \left(\frac{8}{\pi m}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{N_A}{(kT)^{\frac{3}{2}} G(T)} \int_0^\infty \sum_\mu \frac{(2I^\mu + 1)}{(2I^0 + 1)} \times \sigma^\mu(E) E e^{-\frac{E+E_x^\mu}{kT}} dE \quad (1)$$

where I^μ and E_x^μ are the spins and excitation energies of the various levels, k is the Boltzmann constant, m is the reduced mass, N_A is the Avogadro number, and $G(T) = \sum_\mu (2I^\mu + 1)/(2I^0 + 1) \exp(-E_x^\mu/kT)$.

For the ^{90}Zr nucleus, the α potential of Demetriou and Goriely (cyan dotted line, Figure 1) gave the best agreement. Its calculated *rms* error was 0.0495. The theoretical predictions employing this α OMP were within the acceptable ranges of all data points except at 9.5 and 11.5 MeV. The predictions of the Nolte *et al.* α potential were off by an order of magnitude at lower energies, while slowly approaching the acceptable range at higher energies. For the ^{121}Sb nucleus, the α OMP of Avrigeanu *et al.* (black dotted line, Figure 2) gave the best agreement by far. The theoretical predictions of this potential agreed with all the data points except one at 11 MeV. Its *rms* error was 0.0081. The predictions of all other α potentials were greatly off, as none lied within the acceptable range of experimental data points. The potential of Nolte *et al.* came close, systematically overestimating the cross sections at all energies. Similarly, for the ^{151}Eu nucleus, only the α potential of Avrigeanu *et al.* (black dotted line, Figure 3) provided the optimum fit. Its calculated *rms* error was 0.0391. The predictions were within the acceptable range of 5 data points out of 13, while the rest of the potentials were off by a large margin. The potential of Nolte *et al.* came second, agreeing only with the cross sections at around 17 MeV. Finally, for the ^{162}Er nucleus, the α potential of Avrigeanu *et al.* (black dotted line, Figure 4) agreed best with experiment based on the least *rms* error of 0.1796. Its predictions were within the acceptable range of experiment at around 14 MeV, while agreeing with the rest of data points within an order of magnitude. The agreement for this nucleus was by far the worst based on the *rms* error, and can be seen in the plot.

Collections of reaction rates, commonly referred to as libraries, are core nuclear physics inputs to the simulation of astrophysical environments [15]. Therefore, it is important that they must be constrained with the experimental data. Using the constrained model combinations in our study, we calculated the thermonuclear reaction rates at temperatures $T_9 = (1 - 10)$. The computations are depicted in Table 1. As expected, it was observed that as the nuclear charge increased, the relative rates decreased by orders of magnitude at same temperatures. When comparing with the

Figure 1: The calculated cross sections for the $^{90}\text{Zr}(\alpha,\gamma)^{94}\text{Mo}$ process along with the comparison data.

Figure 2: The calculated cross sections for the $^{121}\text{Sb}(\alpha,\gamma)^{125}\text{I}$ process along with the comparison data.

Figure 3: The calculated cross sections for the $^{151}\text{Eu}(\alpha, \gamma)^{155}\text{Tb}$ process along with the comparison data.

Figure 4: The calculated cross sections for the $^{162}\text{Er}(\alpha,\gamma)^{166}\text{Yb}$ process along with the comparison data.

investigation of Kelmar *et al.* [9], the $^{90}\text{Zr}(\alpha,\gamma)$ rates were found to be higher by a factor of 3 at lower energies, while agreeing well at higher energies.

Table 1: The thermonuclear (α,γ) rates in units of $\text{cm}^3\text{s}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$.

T_9	$^{90}\text{Zr}(\alpha,\gamma)$	$^{121}\text{Sb}(\alpha,\gamma)$	$^{151}\text{Eu}(\alpha,\gamma)$	$^{162}\text{Er}(\alpha,\gamma)$
1.0	9.49×10^{-22}	8.98×10^{-25}	1.22×10^{-29}	7.72×10^{-32}
1.5	2.21×10^{-15}	1.02×10^{-17}	1.86×10^{-21}	5.21×10^{-23}
2.0	1.38×10^{-11}	1.27×10^{-13}	8.37×10^{-17}	4.19×10^{-18}
2.5	6.55×10^{-9}	8.32×10^{-11}	1.33×10^{-13}	9.68×10^{-15}
3.0	6.29×10^{-7}	9.37×10^{-9}	3.22×10^{-11}	3.17×10^{-12}
3.5	1.98×10^{-5}	3.12×10^{-7}	2.15×10^{-9}	2.87×10^{-10}
4.0	2.83×10^{-4}	4.27×10^{-6}	5.44×10^{-8}	9.97×10^{-9}
5.0	1.21×10^{-2}	1.34×10^{-4}	4.41×10^{-6}	1.32×10^{-6}
6.0	1.36×10^{-1}	9.07×10^{-4}	5.31×10^{-5}	1.97×10^{-5}
7.0	6.39×10^{-1}	3.00×10^{-3}	1.98×10^{-4}	8.32×10^{-5}
8.0	$1.61 \times 10^{+0}$	7.71×10^{-3}	4.07×10^{-4}	1.92×10^{-4}
9.0	$2.67 \times 10^{+0}$	1.67×10^{-2}	6.49×10^{-4}	3.26×10^{-4}
10	$3.50 \times 10^{+0}$	2.98×10^{-2}	9.09×10^{-4}	4.63×10^{-4}

3 Conclusion

The cross sections for the (α,γ) reactions on p -nuclei: ^{90}Zr , ^{121}Sb , ^{151}Eu , and ^{162}Er were calculated within the framework of the statistical model code TALYS-1.96. The α optical potential model variations were produced and the best fits were deduced based upon the least calculated *rms* error. It was found that the α potential of Demetriou and Goriely produced the best fit for ^{90}Zr , while the α potential of Avrigeanu *et al.* performing best for the rest of nuclei. The potential of Nolte *et al.* systemically overestimated, while the rest of the potentials generally underestimated the cross sections. Based upon the best fitted models, we calculated the thermonuclear reaction rates that can serve as constrained inputs to various astrophysical models.

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